

MAJOR MACROECONOMIC INDICATORS AND THEIR FUNCTION

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Abstract: This article describes macroeconomics, the main macroeconomic indicators in our country and their function.

Key words: Macroeconomics, inflation, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Consumer Price Index (CPI), Indicator.

Macroeconomics is the economy at the level of the national economy, which unites material production and non-material sectors at the country level. Macroeconomics began to form as an independent scientific direction in the early 1930s. 20th century, the formation of microeconomics corresponds to the last years of the 19th century (L. Walras, K. Menger, A. Marshall). The basics of macroeconomics were created by John Maynard Keynes. J. Keynes in his book "The General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money" (1936) proved the possibility of a stable unemployment rate and underutilization of production capacities in a market economy.

Macroeconomics includes material and non-material production and service sectors of the national economy. Interdependence and balanced development of all branches and production areas is required for the functioning and stable growth of the national economy.

The volume of production, service provision and their growth in the national economy is determined and analyzed at the macro-economic level through a number of indicators. Through macroeconomic indicators, the state of the entire economy is analyzed and a conclusion is drawn.

Indicators expressing the economic situation of a particular country are called macroeconomic indicators. Macroeconomic indicators are grouped into quantitative and qualitative indicators. Macroeconomic quantitative indicators represent the economy of certain countries, while qualitative indicators reflect the economy of these countries in a relative manner. Macroeconomic quantitative indicators include the following indicators: Gross domestic product (GDP), net domestic product (SIM), national income (MD), personal income (ShD), disposable income (ID), etc. Indicators of macroeconomic quality include such indicators as: inflation growth rate, unemployment rate, employment rate of the population, gross domestic product per capita, etc.

The interrelationship between macroeconomic indicators can be expressed through the system of national accounts as follows;

1. Gross production of all branches - intermediate consumption = Gross domestic product.
2. Gross domestic product - depreciation = net domestic product.
3. Net domestic product - indirect taxes on business = national income
4. National income - social security contributions - taxes on corporate profits - retained earnings of the corporation + transfer payments = personal income.
5. Personal income - personal taxes = discretionary income.

Both natural and value indicators are used to express the volume of production. However, it is impossible to measure the volume of production of the national economy in natural units,

because here we are talking about millions of goods and services that cannot be compared with each other.

That is why value indicators are used to express the volume and composition of national production. These indicators are determined using two quantities:

- volume of natural form of production; - price level.

In practice, two types of prices are used in the national accounting system: - current or real prices;

- fixed or comparable basic prices.

Macroeconomics deals with concepts such as GDP, GNI, aggregate demand, aggregate supply, balance of payments, money market, goods market, and labor market. A system of generalized indicators showing the state and development of the country's economy - national wealth, gross domestic product, gross national product, net national product, national income, population income, the sum of state and private investments, the total amount of money in circulation, etc. Aggregate, summarizing indicators for the total economy are objects of macroeconomics study. Current or effective prices for the current year are used to determine the relationship between production and consumption of a product during the year and reflect the financial value aspects of reproduction. But it is not appropriate to use current prices to analyze production over a certain period of time. Because any increase or decrease in them directly affects the size of the gross domestic product and national income, distorting the real state of the economy. Constant prices are used to give a true assessment of the development of the national economy. Constant or comparative prices are the prices of products in a given year, which are used in the value assessment of the volume of production for the analyzed period. These prices allow for changes in the natural volume of production and reflect actual changes in production over a period of time.

The amount that shows the change in the volume of production of the gross domestic product with the increase in prices is called the general price index of all finished goods and services or deflator. GDP includes millions of created goods, and it is impossible to physically observe the price of each of them. That is why the deflator is determined using a market basket. The market basket includes important goods and services that are part of the gross domestic product and make up its main part. Changes in the prices of goods and services included in the market basket are constantly monitored by statistical agencies, and on this basis, a general price index or deflator is calculated.

In economic practice, along with the deflator, another indicator of the level of inflation is widely used - the consumer price index (INI) or the cost of living index. The consumer price index reflects the change in the value of a set of services and consumer booms recorded in the current year compared to the base year. In other words, with the help of this index, it is possible to determine how the cost of living or standard of living of each person, family and the entire population is changing.

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